

1 **The challenge of defining “sustainable growing media”:** Why the term is 2 **used incorrectly and what needs to be done about it**

3

4 **Abstract**

5 The term “sustainable growing media” is widely used in horticultural research, policy,
6 and industry, yet its meaning remains ambiguous, inconsistently applied, and often
7 unsupported by evidence, undermining the very decisions it is meant to guide. Materials
8 are frequently characterised as sustainable based on single attributes, such as being
9 peat-free, recycled, renewable or aligned with policy priorities, without demonstrating
10 reliable horticultural performance, economic viability, social responsibility or reduced
11 environmental impact within real production systems. This paper examines why defining
12 sustainable growing media has proven persistently challenging and why a single,
13 universal definition may be neither achievable nor even useful. Drawing on existing
14 literature and policy initiatives, we analyse sustainability through its environmental,
15 economic and social pillars, highlighting how narrow or assumption-based assessments
16 obscure trade-offs and shift, rather than reduce, environmental and social burdens. We
17 argue that sustainability in growing media is not an inherent material property but a
18 context-dependent outcome that must be demonstrated within a defined production
19 system. Rather than proposing a new definition, we outline eight minimum conditions
20 for responsible use of the term, emphasising measurable impacts, functional
21 performance, economic feasibility, and explicit treatment of trade-offs. Where such
22 evidence is lacking, precise, verifiable descriptors should replace broad sustainability
23 claims.

24 **Keywords:** Sustainability assessment, peat and peat alternatives, horticultural functionality,
25 environmental trade-offs, soilless production systems, policy and material classification,
26 compost, potting soils, substrates

27 **1. Introduction**

28 The concept of sustainability is widely assumed to be self-evident and inherently
29 supportive of the greater good, yet it has become increasingly detached from its original

30 meaning of maintaining a specific system continually (Grober and Cunningham, 2012;
31 Kidd, 1992; von Carlowitz, 1713). In the growing media literature, the term has been
32 discussed critically for more than a decade, with several influential reviews attempting
33 to clarify its meaning and guide material development and assessment (Barrett et al.,
34 2016; Bilderback et al., 2013; Carlile and Coules, 2013; Carlile et al., 2015; Caron and
35 Rochefort, 2013). Nevertheless, the term remains inconsistently applied and is
36 frequently used to describe materials based on assumed environmental benefit, often
37 without measurement, and before their ability to sustain viable crop production has
38 been demonstrated. This is not unique to growing media but is particularly evident even
39 in comprehensive overviews of the field (e.g. Gruda et al., 2024), where sustainability
40 serves as a guiding aspiration rather than a measurable standard for the materials being
41 assessed.

42 Growing media (commonly known as potting soils or substrates) are defined as
43 materials other than soil in situ, the function of which is to support the growth of plants
44 or mushrooms (Caron et al., 2023; European Parliament and Council, 2019). Their
45 purpose is to regulate water, air, and nutrient dynamics within a container confined
46 root/mycelium volume. In addition, they must meet practical constraints related to
47 weight, structure, handling, consistency, and availability at scale. In practice, relatively
48 few materials have consistently met these requirements across crops and production
49 systems while also being available at scale (Gruda et al., 2023; Himanshu et al., 2026;
50 Hirschler and Thrän, 2023; Koseoglu and Roberts, 2025; Schmilewski, 2008).

51 Historically, horticultural peat and, more recently, coconut coir have occupied this role
52 in organic growing media, while mineral wool has become widely established in soilless
53 vegetable and cut-flower production. However, all are subject to environmental and/or
54 social scrutiny, whether related to peatland degradation and carbon emissions for peat,
55 long-distance transport and supply chain conditions for coir, or non-biodegradability
56 and end-of-life disposal for mineral wool.

57 In practice, materials such as compost, wood fibre, bark, coir or biochar are often
58 described as sustainable based on characteristics such as being non-peat, recycled,
59 renewable or associated with favourable environmental expectations (Gruda, 2019;
60 Hirschler and Thrän, 2023). However, none of these characterisations, on their own,

61 convey whether the material can sustain horticultural production in terms of quality,
62 economic viability, and supply. Nor do they even necessarily demonstrate reduced
63 environmental impact at a system level (Barrett et al., 2016; Goglio et al., 2025).
64 Sustainability is therefore often framed narrowly in selected environmental concerns
65 that are weakly specified or insufficiently quantified, while production performance and
66 economic feasibility (e.g. at a commercial greenhouse scale) are treated as secondary
67 considerations, left untested or not stated at all.

68 A newly formulated growing medium with adequate properties is expected to perform
69 more or less as reliably as the growing medium it will replace, particularly in a sector
70 characterised by low margins and limited tolerance for production risk (Brumfield et al.,
71 2015; Wei et al., 2020). A growing medium that substantially increases production risk or
72 reduces yield can undermine the very system it is meant to support, regardless of its
73 environmental intent. Therefore, sustainability claims that are not grounded in
74 demonstrated production performance therefore provide little practical guidance and
75 may obscure, rather than reduce, environmental, economic, and social risk.

76 This tension between functional reliability and environmental concern forms the
77 backdrop against which sustainability has emerged as a central concept in growing
78 media research. However, the term “sustainable growing media” is widely used without
79 a consistent or operational meaning, creating ambiguity for researchers, manufacturers,
80 policymakers and growers who must evaluate and apply such claims in practice. In this
81 paper we examine why the term “sustainable growing media” is persistently challenging
82 to define, describe, and apply in a useful and science-based manner. Rather than
83 proposing a fixed definition, we analyse what the term can reasonably be taken to mean
84 when applied to growing media and offer guidance on how it should and should not be
85 used in research, policy, and manufacturing.

86 **2. Definitions of sustainability**

87 The concept underlying sustainability was first formally articulated by Hans Carl von
88 Carlowitz (1713) in the context of forestry, where it referred to the careful management
89 of an indispensable resource so that it remained continuously available. In this original

90 sense, sustainability was explicitly practical and system specific. It concerned
91 continuity, reliability, and the long-term maintenance of essential functions.

92 Nearly three centuries later the Brundtland Commission (1987) reframed sustainability,
93 defining it as meeting present needs without compromising the ability of future
94 generations to meet their own. The reframing included broadening the scope from long-
95 term, economically feasible production to a generalised higher level that further
96 includes ecological and societal goals. While this has been foundational for
97 international policy, its meaning becomes diffuse and less well defined when
98 transferred from societal systems to individual materials or products.

99 The subsequent consolidation of sustainability into three pillars (environmental,
100 economic, and social) was intended to make the concept more operational (UN World
101 Summit 2005). However, this framework provides little guidance on how these
102 dimensions should be prioritised or balanced when trade-offs arise (Purvis et al., 2019).
103 In technically constrained sectors such as horticulture, where materials must satisfy
104 strict functional requirements and supply realities, these trade-offs between pillars of
105 sustainability are unavoidable.

106 **2.1 Past attempts to define “sustainable growing media”**

107 Efforts to define sustainable growing media have remained unresolved due to these
108 broader conceptual challenges. One of the most ambitious efforts took place in the
109 United Kingdom between 2011 and 2013, when a multi-stakeholder task force
110 undertook the development of a shared definition (Knight, 2012). Despite an
111 unprecedented collaboration across industry, retailers, NGOs, and government
112 (Dawson, 2012), no agreed definition emerged. The process attempted to address
113 aspects of all three sustainability pillars but recognised the complexity of measurement
114 and how incomplete the assessment really was, with the narrative changing from
115 ‘sustainable’ to ‘responsible’ (Alexander and Bragg, 2013).

116 Thus, focus shifted away from defining sustainability toward concepts that could be
117 operationalised, such as the ‘Responsible Sourcing Scheme in the UK’¹, “Renewable raw

¹ <https://responsiblesourcing.org.uk/key-documents/>

118 materials” in the Dutch ‘Covenant on the Environmental Impact of Potting Soil and
119 Substrates’², ‘Responsibly Produced Peat’³ and more recently, ‘Responsibly Produced
120 Coir’⁴. Criteria for responsible sourcing could be specified, audited, and enforced,
121 whereas sustainability remained too difficult to codify. As a result, “sustainable growing
122 media” persisted as an aspirational label without clear operational content, while
123 governance moved toward narrower, verifiable proxies. National initiatives targeting
124 reductions in horticultural peat use, such as the German ‘Peat Use Reduction Strategy’⁵
125 and the Swiss ‘Peat exit plan’⁶, are also examples of easily verifiable proxies (peat
126 volumes/percentages) but largely lack measurements of sustainability at growing media
127 or horticultural levels. The German label ‘HORTICERT’⁷ has attempted to address this by
128 certifying that peat substitute materials meet certain ecological, social and economic
129 standards across their production chain, including a standardised values for
130 greenhouse gas emissions derived from the Growing Media Environmental Footprint
131 Guideline (Bennett, 2021; Sentinella, 2024). However, these metrics are somewhat
132 arbitrary, peat is excluded from certification, and there is no required demonstration of
133 horticultural performance.

134 **3. The three pillars of sustainable growing media**

135 The difficulty of defining sustainable growing media is closely tied to the three-pillar
136 framework itself (Figure 1). Sustainability claims depend on which pillar is emphasised
137 (Carlile and Coules, 2013). Environmental objectives have often prioritised peat
138 reduction and the promotion of non-peat materials (often without impact
139 measurement), social considerations have often focused on the labour conditions of
140 coir production, while economic considerations have emphasised quality and
141 consistency, cost control, and continuity of supply. For growing media, this has allowed
142 materials to be characterised as sustainable or unsustainable depending on

² <https://convenantpotgrond.nl/over-het-convenant/>

³ <https://www.responsiblyproducedpeat.org/en/what-we-do>

⁴ <https://www.rhp.nl/en/responsibly-produced-coir>

⁵ <https://www.bmlch.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/EN/Publications/peat-use-reduction-strategy.html>

⁶ <https://www.bafu.admin.ch/en/peat>

⁷ <https://www.horticert.org/>

143 perspective or opinion, even when the evidence base is limited or even contradictory.
144 The result is that the term often fails to convey clear, common, or even correct criteria.

145 **3.1 Environmental sustainability**

146 For most stakeholders, sustainability in growing media is primarily associated with
147 environmental outcomes and treated as an inherent material property. However, even
148 within this limited scope, terminology is used inconsistently and claims often rely on
149 assumptions rather than quantified impacts. Peat is frequently cited as environmentally
150 unsustainable due to its association with carbon emissions, peatland degradation and
151 biodiversity loss (Gruda, 2019; Gruda et al., 2024, 2023). While environmental impacts
152 of peat extraction are well documented (Chapman et al., 2003), justification is often
153 based on overly broad qualitative statements or global peatland statistics without
154 adequate contextualisation to extraction practices, use intensity, or substitution effects
155 (Hirschler and Osterburg, 2022; Koseoglu and Roberts, 2025; Prasad et al., 2024).
156 Oversimplifications are also observed for other materials including coconut coir
157 (Hirschler et al., 2022), where environmental assessments can overlook saline
158 wastewater generation during processing (Woznicki et al., 2024); wood-based materials,
159 where renewability alone does not reflect processing emissions or nitrogen
160 immobilisation during use (Atzori et al., 2021); mineral materials (e.g., mineral wool,
161 expanded perlite), where questions of non-biodegradability, recyclability, and end-of-life
162 treatment are frequently overlooked; and societal side-stream materials (e.g., green
163 compost, composts, solid digestates), where impacts related to transportation, nutrient
164 losses and emissions during processing are inconsistently addressed (Raviv, 2013).
165 Moreover, the use of materials that fail to meet functional requirements can itself
166 increase environmental impacts by reducing production efficiency and increasing
167 resource use at the crop system level. In practice, all materials have environmental
168 impacts (Quantis, 2012; Stichnothe, 2022), and it is necessary to make comparisons
169 that objectively consider footprints of both the growing media and overall crop
170 production.

171 Life cycle assessment (LCA) provides the most established framework for comparing
172 environmental impacts of growing media, enabling assessment across multiple
173 categories, including climate change, acidification, eutrophication, ecotoxicity, land use

174 and water consumption (Pryshlakivsky and Searcy, 2013). However, comparability
175 between studies remains limited due to variation in assumptions, system boundaries,
176 functional units, reporting formats and data quality (Weidema et al., 2018). Recent
177 European initiatives have aimed to address these limitations through standardised
178 Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) methodologies, including sector specific
179 category rules (CR) for horticultural products (FloriPEFCR for cut flowers and potted
180 plants, Broekema et al., 2024; and FreshProducePEFCR for fruits and vegetables,
181 Weststrate et al., 2024) including growing media (Growing Media Environmental
182 Footprint Guidelines; Bennett, 2021; Sentinella, 2024). These frameworks standardise
183 assessment across sixteen environmental impact categories by defining system
184 boundaries, functional units and data quality requirements, and include an aggregated
185 single-score indicator based on European Commission weightings, reducing the risk of
186 cherry-picking individual metrics such as carbon footprint while ignoring others.

187

188 Environmental sustainability factors that are not comprehensively or directly captured
189 within standard LCA frameworks, but are nonetheless important, are biodiversity
190 effects, nature conservation outcomes, renewability of materials, and end-of-life
191 considerations such as reuse or recycling (circularity). While these aspects should be
192 better considered, they only add clarity when their boundaries and limitations are
193 explicitly defined. Evidence of reuse potential exists for some growing media under
194 controlled conditions (Vandecasteele et al., 2024; Woznicki et al., 2024), but
195 environmental performance alone is insufficient to justify broader sustainability claims
196 without concurrent consideration of functionality, economic feasibility and social
197 implications.

198

199 **3.2 Economic sustainability**

200 Economic sustainability is necessary for the adoption of novel growing media in
201 horticultural production. It determines whether materials and practices can move
202 beyond experimental or niche applications and be maintained at commercial scale. In
203 this context, economic sustainability refers not only to product affordability, but to the

204 capacity of the system to generate stable value across the entire life cycle and value
205 chain (Auer et al., 2017), while supporting reliable horticultural production.

206 Conceptually, the economic dimension operates at three interlinked levels: (i)
207 manufacturing, (ii) use, and (iii) reuse or refurbishment, as well as for diverse market
208 segments (e.g. hobby, professional). At the manufacturing level, economic sustainability
209 depends on the cost, availability and consistency of raw materials, processing
210 requirements, energy and water inputs, logistics and quality assurance. These factors
211 directly affect production costs, scalability and supply continuity, which are critical for
212 both conventional and alternative growing media constituents. At the use level,
213 economic performance is inseparable from horticultural function. Growing media
214 influence yield stability, crop duration, water and nutrient use efficiency, disease
215 pressure and management complexity. Any increase in variability, risk or compensatory
216 inputs translates into economic penalties for growers and reduces adoption likelihood.
217 At the reuse or refurbishment level, economic sustainability is linked to the feasibility of
218 nutrient recycling, processing costs, quality retention and risk mitigation when spent
219 media are reintroduced into production systems. While reuse of spent growing media
220 has been demonstrated under controlled research conditions for materials such as peat
221 and coir (Vandecasteele et al., 2024; Woznicki et al., 2024), commercial-scale
222 implementation remains limited. The costs of sterilisation, quality testing and logistical
223 handling often exceed those of virgin material, particularly as substrate prices decrease
224 with scale. Economic viability of reuse therefore depends strongly on local conditions,
225 material type and available infrastructure, and cannot be assumed from research-scale
226 results alone.

227 Assessing economic sustainability remains challenging. Economic indicators are often
228 fragmented, context-specific and weakly integrated into sustainability assessments.

229 While life cycle approaches increasingly address environmental impacts, the economic
230 pillar is frequently reduced to product price or omitted altogether (Ruett et al., 2024).

231 Robust, peer-reviewed frameworks that systematically connect manufacturing costs,
232 crop performance (Vinci and Rapa, 2019) and end-of-life options are scarce, despite
233 repeated calls for integrated evaluation. As a result, economic claims around alternative

234 growing media are often based on short-term trials, optimistic assumptions of scale-up,
235 or non-transparent industry data, rather than reproducible scientific evidence.

236 A pragmatic way forward is to operationalise economic sustainability through a limited
237 but structured set of indicators spanning the three life-cycle phases, including
238 manufacturing costs, raw material availability, affordability, scalability and quality
239 consistency, crop performance and input efficiency during use, and the costs and
240 benefits of reuse or refurbishment (see Figure 1). Strengthening the scientific basis of
241 these indicators is essential, as economic viability remains a primary driver of adoption
242 and a prerequisite for achieving environmental and social sustainability in horticultural
243 soilless systems.

244 **3.3 Social sustainability**

245 Without explicit attention to health, safety, social impact, and functionality risk
246 distribution, environmentally motivated raw material substitution in growing media may
247 shift social burdens and risks (such as impacts on worker safety, labour conditions, or
248 local communities) rather than reducing them. Yet social sustainability remains the
249 least specified pillar for growing media assessments and the most underdeveloped. It
250 encompasses labour conditions and community impacts in constituent production,
251 occupational health and safety during manufacturing and use, and transparency and
252 traceability across often complex global supply chains (Figure 1).

253 Public and occupational health have increasingly become prominent as more recycled
254 and side-stream organic materials are incorporated into growing media. Under certain
255 conditions, for example where poorly composted materials are used, these inputs may
256 introduce pathogenic microorganisms and other microbiological hazards or exposure
257 risks (Alsanius et al., 2025). While such risks do not undermine the value of circularity,
258 they highlight the need for explicit risk analysis, control measures, and good processing
259 techniques. Clear communication of risks and material quality from producers and
260 quality assurance bodies to growers, regulators and other relevant stakeholders is also
261 essential. Environmental indicators alone cannot capture these dimensions. Social
262 sustainability therefore involves not only aggregate benefits but also how risks and
263 burdens are distributed across workers, growers, consumers and communities.

264 Social impacts in growing media can be measured using social certification standards
265 or social life cycle assessment (S-LCA) frameworks. S-LCA combines global databases,
266 sector/country indicators, and company-level data. These approaches follow
267 international guidelines developed by UNEP and SETAC and consider multiple
268 stakeholder groups (workers, local communities, consumers, and value chain actors)
269 across impact categories such as human rights, labour rights, occupational health and
270 safety, governance, community infrastructure, and economic development. While past
271 growing media LCAs included a human health impact category (Paoli et al., 2022;
272 Quantis, 2012; Vinci and Rapa, 2019), these are often insufficient and few provided a
273 social assessment (Toboso-Chavero et al., 2021), underscoring the need to integrate S-
274 LCA with environmental and economic assessments.

275 Within S-LCA, social risks are often quantified using indicators such as weighted labour
276 “risk hours” derived from commercial databases (e.g., the Social Hotspots Database
277 (Norris et al., 2013), aggregated across country, sector and company levels. Company-
278 level assessments rely on primary data (e.g., questionnaires) covering health and safety,
279 gender equality, child labour, wages, working hours, and community engagement, but
280 data availability and report quality remain limiting factors.

281 Overall, social sustainability in growing media requires moving beyond absent or partial
282 indicators towards integrated, life-cycle-based assessments that address social
283 conditions, health risks and governance throughout the life cycle. Evidence-based
284 evaluation depends not only on cumulative performance metrics but also on
285 understanding who benefits, who bears risk, and how social impacts are managed and
286 communicated across the supply chain.

287 **3.4 Trade-offs and system dependency**

288 The three-pillar framework presents sustainability as a balanced outcome but offers
289 little guidance for resolving trade-offs when balance cannot be achieved. For growing
290 media, these trade-offs are unavoidable and strongly system dependent. Materials are
291 selected not on abstract sustainability attributes, but on their ability to meet crop-
292 specific functional requirements under practical, economic and risk constraints. As a
293 result, environmental, economic and social performance cannot be assessed

294 independently of production context (Barrett et al., 2016; Carlile et al., 2015; Gruda,
295 2019).

296 Evidence from both research and practice shows that some materials promoted as
297 sustainable often face limitations related to feedstock variability, processing
298 requirements, logistics, cost and biosecurity risk (Litterick et al., 2025). When these
299 factors are included, environmental rankings may change direction, and improvements
300 in one sustainability dimension can coincide with increased burdens in others (Toboso-
301 Chavero et al., 2021). We therefore advocate that sustainability in growing media should
302 rather be understood as a conditional, system-level outcome than a fixed material
303 property, and as such require explicit acknowledgement of trade-offs, uncertainty and
304 context-specific constraints rather than binary classifications.

305 **4. Discussion**

306 The difficulty of defining “sustainable growing media” lies less in the absence of suitable
307 materials than in the tendency to treat sustainability as an intrinsic attribute rather than
308 a conditional outcome. We have shown sustainability claims in growing media routinely
309 collapse complex, system-dependent considerations into simplified labels that are
310 weakly specified and rarely supported by evidence relevant to production practice. This
311 has allowed the term to persist as an aspirational descriptor while masking unresolved
312 trade-offs and shifting, rather than reducing, environmental, economic, or social
313 burdens.

314 Rather than proposing a new definition, or abandoning the concept altogether, we
315 recommend a set of minimum conditions for the responsible use of the term (Box 1).
316 These conditions are intentionally modest. They do not require comprehensive
317 assessment in all cases, but they do require transparency, explicit scope, and
318 proportional evidence. Sustainability claims should specify the production context to
319 which they apply, identify which dimensions are being addressed, and avoid implying
320 benefits beyond the evidence presented. Framing sustainability as comparative and
321 conditional (e.g. “more environmentally sustainable based on measured climate
322 impact”), rather than absolute (i.e. “sustainable”, “not sustainable”), offers a more
323 scientifically defensible and practically useful basis for decision-making.

324 Our recommendations have practical implications across research, industry, and policy.
325 For research, they reinforce the need to link environmental assessments to functional
326 performance and feasibility, and to report assumptions, boundaries, and uncertainty
327 with sufficient clarity to enable interpretation and comparison. For industry, they clarify
328 that material substitution alone does not justify sustainability claims unless reliable
329 performance and supply can also be demonstrated for the intended system. In such
330 cases, narrower descriptors (such as responsible sourcing, quantified environmental
331 indicators, or demonstrated reuse potential) provide more accurate and verifiable
332 communication. For policy, the findings help explain why proxy-based targets can
333 support transition objectives but cannot be conflated with sustainability outcomes at
334 the growing media or production system level.

335 The three-pillar framework specifically for growing media (Figure 1) which we have
336 presented, also has clear limits. Sustainability trade-offs cannot be eliminated, and no
337 single model can resolve how competing objectives should be weighted across all crops
338 and systems. Life-cycle-based tools remain sensitive to methodological choices, while
339 social and economic indicators are unevenly developed. While we did not try to resolve
340 these challenges here, we have hopefully made them more visible and discourage
341 claims that imply a level of certainty that current evidence cannot support.

342 Future progress will depend less on redefining sustainability and more on improving how
343 evidence is generated and communicated. At present, no simple or cost-effective set of
344 criteria exists that can reliably support sustainability claims across the diversity of
345 growing media and production systems. Addressing this gap requires further
346 methodological and empirical work. Priority areas include integrating functional
347 performance with environmental and economic assessment, improving transparency
348 around processing and supply-chain impacts, and developing approaches that better
349 capture risk, uncertainty, and distributional effects.

350 We present this contribution as a call for more systematic and coordinated research,
351 rather than as a finalised assessment framework. Sustainability in growing media
352 should be treated as an evolving, system-level outcome that must be demonstrated
353 within a defined production system rather than a fixed label. By applying the minimum
354 conditions outlined here and using precise terminology where evidence is limited, the

355 growing media literature and sector can move toward clearer, unbiased, more credible,
356 and more useful sustainability claims.

Accepted Version

357 Figure 1. Conceptual representation of sustainability in growing media as an outcome of the
 358 combined fulfilment of environmental, social, and economic conditions. Each pillar represents
 359 key dimensions relevant to sustainability claims. Assessment should be based on growing
 360 media properties within a defined production and use context (cropping system). Sustainability
 361 is not inherent to individual materials or single attributes, but emerges from the joint
 362 consideration of performance, context, and impacts across all three pillars.

363

364

365 Box 1. Recommendations for the use of the term “sustainable growing media”. Based
366 on the analysis in our paper, we make the following recommendations to define
367 minimum conditions for its meaningful and responsible use in research, policy, and
368 industry contexts.

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Recommendations for the use of the term “sustainable growing media”

1. Consider all three pillars of sustainability explicitly

Sustainability claims should address **environmental, economic, and social dimensions**. Improvement in one pillar must not be assumed to imply improvement in others. Where one or more pillars are not assessed, this limitation should be stated clearly.

2. Specify which sustainability pillar(s) are being addressed

When full three-pillar assessment is not feasible, claims should be explicitly scoped (e.g. “reduced climate impact under stated assumptions” or “verified responsible sourcing”). Broad, unqualified sustainability claims should be avoided.

3. Frame sustainability at the system level, not the material level

Growing media sustainability should be evaluated within a defined production system, including crop type, production scale, management practices, and supply chains. Sustainability is a context-dependent outcome, not an intrinsic material property. This is especially true for growing media, which are only one part of horticultural production.

4. Measure impacts rather than infer them from material categories

Assumptions based on labels such as “peat-free”, “renewable”, “recycled”, or “biogenic” are insufficient and misleading. Sustainability claims should, wherever possible, be supported by measured indicators (e.g. environmental Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Cost (LCC), Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA), performance trials) with transparent methods and stated limitations.

5. Demonstrate functional and economic performance for the intended use

Growing media described as sustainable should demonstrate reliable horticultural performance, economic feasibility, and supply continuity for the system in which they are promoted. Materials that disproportionately increase production risk or require compensatory inputs cannot be assumed to reduce overall sustainability.

6. Make trade-offs and uncertainties explicit

Trade-offs within and between sustainability pillars are unavoidable and should be acknowledged rather than obscured. Where results depend strongly on assumptions, data quality, or system boundaries, this dependency must be made transparent.

7. Avoid absolute or binary sustainability claims

Terms such as “sustainable”, “unsustainable”, or “fully sustainable” should not be used without qualification. Sustainability should be framed as **comparative, directional, and conditional**, not absolute.

8. Use precise, verifiable descriptors where evidence is limited

Where comprehensive sustainability assessment is not available, it is preferable to use specific and verifiable descriptors (e.g. “responsibly sourced”, “quantified carbon footprint under stated assumptions”, “demonstrated reuse potential”) rather than the blanket term “sustainable”.

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